

SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING IN THE SELECTED ENTERPRISES IN THE CITY OF SAN PABLO, LAGUNA

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ABSTRACT

The study was about the utilization of social media marketing in the selected enterprises in the City of San Pablo, Laguna. The quantitative approach is used in this study to ascertain social media marketing adoption in SMEs as well as marketing strategies and challenges and proportional random sampling technique to analyze 374 owners and managers of the SME's. Moreover, the research made use of a self-made survey questionnaire instrument in data gathering. The frequency count and percentage were utilized to ascertain the business profile of the respondents in terms of nature of business, years of operation, and monthly revenue of the business. Mean and Standard Deviation were used to determine the perception of the respondents in terms of the extent of utilization of social media marketing of the respondents. Kruskal Wallis Test was used to test the difference between the business profile and the utilization of social media marketing in SMEs. This research aims to evaluate the academic literature regarding the potential and difficulties of using social media marketing in the selected enterprises (SMEs), as well as to suggest marketing strategies and obstacles to decide the use of social media marketing in SMEs. The study recommended marketing best practices aimed to improve the use of social media marketing.

Keywords: *social media marketing, social media, interactivity, informativeness, personalization, trendiness, word of mouth.*

INTRODUCTION

In the fast-paced digital landscape of the 21st century, the emergence of social media has revolutionized the way businesses connect with their target audience. Social media marketing is already an essential component of contemporary marketing best practices enabling organizations to harness the power of online communities and platforms to promote products, services, and brands (Gamundoy et al, 2020). As a dynamic and ever-evolving field, social media marketing requires constant adaptation and creativity to effectively engage with the audience in an environment that is subject to rapid change (Smith, 2020). On the other hand, SME's find themselves at the intersection of opportunity and challenge. These nimble and innovative businesses, often constrained by limited resources, have been presented with a unique avenue for growth and market expansion through social media marketing. As SMEs navigate the complex landscape of modern commerce, harnessing the potential of social media platforms has become a pivotal strategy (Anderson, 2021).

Jamil et al (2022) stated that social media has the potential to serve as an effective promotional instrument for attracting visits to business pages. Meanwhile, in a study conducted by Cheung et al (2021), it was underscored that the utilization of social listening technologies enables the monitoring of online reach expansion through the examination of a business's connections, fans, and followers.

In a recent study conducted by Farivar and Richardson (2021), it was observed that customers' inclination to persist in using a certain product or service is significantly impacted by their level of pleasure after receiving the service. Based on research in the field of social media studies, it has been found that contentment plays a significant role in influencing individuals' intentions to continue using social media platforms. Consequently, subsequent to availing a service, a consumer will evaluate their level of satisfaction. As noted by Mahendra (2021), the level of consumer satisfaction has a significant impact on their likelihood to engage in repeat purchase intention. Based on the author, the satisfaction of a client with a product or service directly influences their inclination to engage in repeat purchases. The retail industry was significantly impacted by the explosive rise of internet purchasing, which forced traditional brick-and-mortar businesses to change to be competitive in the new retail landscape (McKinsey, 2020). Online revenue was increasing by April 2020, and it was obvious that this tendency will carry over into the post-quarantine era.

Online buying was easy and convenient, but firms needed to be motivated if they were to prosper, especially in eCommerce. Businesses needed to concentrate on their target market, make use of social media platforms, and cultivate consumer trust by offering high-quality content and first-rate customer support if they were to compete in the online marketplace. The term e-commerce, sometimes known as "electronic commerce," describes the buying and selling of goods and services online. As more people utilize the Internet for business and shopping, its popularity has expanded (McKinsey, 2020).

This study's main goal is to determine the difficulties faced by small and medium-sized businesses in San Pablo City, Laguna, as reported by respondents, managers, and business owners. It is anticipated that by better comprehending these obstacles, SMEs would become more competitive and, in due course, develop and expand their enterprises. Regarding the type of business, medium enterprise firm owners with a capitalization of at least 11,000 and ten years of operational experience are most likely to use the service type. They all acknowledged that the numerous requirements in company loan applications provide some challenges when trying to obtain funding. Additionally, because of the significantly lower prices that unregistered businesses are offering on the market, they are vulnerable to the increasingly fierce competition that develops among them. Certain SMEs in this instance have been unable to compete with the microbusinesses. They all dispute that the emphasis on support is solely for microenterprises, and they agree that the LGU does not have enough funding to assist in further developing the SME sector.

Research Questions

The study generally aimed to determine the social media marketing in the selected enterprises in the City of San Pablo, Laguna.

Specifically, the study sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the business profile of the respondents, in terms of:
 - 1.1. nature of business;
 - 1.1. years in operation; and
 - 1.2. monthly revenue?
2. What is the extent of social media utilization with regards to:
 - 2.1. Interactivity;
 - 2.2. Informativeness;
 - 2.3. word of mouth;
 - 2.4. personalization; and
 - 2.5. trendiness?
3. Is there a significant difference between the utilization of social media marketing when grouped according to their business profile of the respondents?
4. What marketing best practices may be shared to enhance the social media in the selected enterprises in San Pablo City, Laguna?

METHODOLOGY

A quantitative method approach design was employed in this study. This method is used to utilized in examining the business profiles of respondents in San Pablo, Laguna, focusing on elements such as the nature of their businesses, years in operation, and monthly revenue. It would also be used in the exploration of variables related to the

utilization of social media marketing for selected enterprises of the City of San Pablo, Laguna in terms of interactivity, informativeness, personalization, trendiness, and word of mouth.

The study focused on the perspectives of the owners and managers of SMEs in San Pablo City regarding the utilization of social media marketing as part of their business strategies. The population size considered for the study was 14,680 registered SMEs. Based on a response distribution of 50%, the recommended sample size was determined to be 374 respondents.

The study parameters were established using the Raosoft calculator to ensure accurate results. The margin of error was set at 5%, indicating the acceptable degree of deviation from the true population parameter. The confidence level was set at 95%, indicating the level of certainty in the obtained results.

Proportional Stratified Random sampling techniques were employed in this research. This involves selecting a sample from a larger population in such a way that each individual or element has an equal chance of being chosen. This method helps ensure that the sample is representative of the entire population, making the results more generalizable and less prone to bias (Creswell, 2014).

The researcher conducted the study in San Pablo, which included selected enterprises and kiosk locations. This survey was carried out through the assistance of the Business Permit and Licensing Office (BPLO). This survey aimed to determine the total number of SMEs operating in the town of San Pablo. The formal request was submitted to the Business Permit and Licensing Office (BPLO) by means of an official written correspondence, which was thereafter transmitted electronically via email. Following the researcher's request for authorization to investigate the quantity of registered SMEs in the town of San Pablo, the survey results were subsequently provided at the San Pablo Capitol. Consequently, it was determined that the total population of SMEs numbered at 14,680 registered establishments classified as small and medium companies SMEs.

In order to collect information from small and medium enterprises in San Pablo City, Laguna, the research instrument for this study was a self-made survey questionnaire. There are two key components to the questionnaire, each of which addresses a different area of the study issue.

The first part is the Business Profile of the respondents. The purpose of this section is to obtain respondents' business-related information. It contains inquiries about the type of business, number of years in operation, and monthly revenue of the SMEs in San Pablo City, Laguna. The second part consists of Extent of Utilization of Social Media Marketing by the respondents. This section analyzes the utilization of social media marketing as perceived by the managers and owners of the SMEs. It includes a series of questions aimed to assess the respondents' thoughts about their preferred option.

A 4-point likerts scale was used to gauge the perception of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) regarding the utilization of social media marketing.

A crucial aspect of this study is the creation of a survey questionnaire that is both valid and trustworthy. The establishment of its validity and reliability is crucial for the successful execution of the study. The initial step will involve doing a comprehensive assessment of existing literature and engaging in consultations with subject matter experts. These activities aimed to develop a questionnaire that effectively encompasses the pertinent constructs and variables. After the formulation of the questionnaire, a group of specialists conduct a comprehensive evaluation to determine its content validity, thereby verifying that the questions are aligned with the objectives of the study. Following the process of content validation, a pilot test is administered to a limited sample of small and medium-sized enterprise (SME) owners and managers in a nearby municipality in Laguna, in order to detect any potential ambiguities or concerns pertaining to the phrasing and structure of the questions. The feedback acquired from the pilot test were utilized to enhance and fine-tune the questionnaire. Additionally, internal consistency metrics such as Cronbach's alpha were obtained at 0.759 interpreted as acceptable.

The researcher carried out the subsequent actions to collect the primary data. Before conducting the study, the researcher first obtain approval from the Dean of the Graduate School of the Pamantasan ng Lungsod ng San Pablo. Once approved, the researcher formally asked for authorization to conduct a survey and personal interview of SMEs in the City of San Pablo, Laguna, with the support of the City Mayor. In parallel, the researcher simultaneously conducted surveys in the area of San Pablo City, Laguna, and retrieved completed questionnaires and interview transcripts the same day. The researcher examined, totaled, and summarized the responses before sending the information to the statistician for data analysis.

The quantitative data collected for this study were analyzed using descriptive statistical tools.

Frequency count and Percentage were used to determine the business profile of the respondents in terms of nature of business, years of operation, and monthly revenue of the business. While,

Mean and Standard Deviation were used to determine the perception of the respondents in terms of the extent of utilization of social media marketing of the respondents. And,

Kruskal Wallis Test was used to test the difference between the business profile and the utilization of social media marketing in SMEs.

In this study, the research objectives revolve around recognizing the utilization of social media marketing in the selected enterprises in San Pablo City, Laguna. The scope of social media platforms includes using Facebook, TikTok, Instagram, WhatsApp, Messenger, Twitter, and reels. The study assessed the level of utilization of social media marketing activities. The study involved a random 374 owners and managers of selected SME's in San Pablo City, Laguna.

DISCUSSION

Table 3.1 Business Profile in terms of Nature of Business

Nature of Business	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Food Service and Accommodation	32	9
Insurance Activities and Financial	38	11
Human Health and Social Work	30	8
Information and Communication,	76	20
Manufacturing	80	21
Other Service Activities	16	4
Professional, Scientific and Technology	43	11
Real Estate Activities	12	3
Wholesale and Retail Trade; Rep	47	13
Overall Mean	374	100.0

The data from table 3.1 demonstrated the company profile in terms of the nature of business. The majority of the respondents were from the manufacturing sector with frequency of 80 (21%). While the sector of real estate has the least number of respondents with a frequency of 12 (3%).

This implies that San Pablo City is a hub of manufacturing business and companies in the regioned, considered as one of the advanced agro-industrial economies in CALABARZON based on DTI-4A data.

Table 3.2 Business Profile in terms of Years in Operation

Years in Operation	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
10 years and below	203	54
11-20 years	77	21
21-30 years	94	25
Overall Mean	374	100

The data from table 3.2 illustrated the business profile in terms of Years in Operation, with the majority of businesses operating for less than 10 years with a frequency of 203 firms (54%). This result implies that many SME's in San Pablo City are still new which can indicate that the business landscapes in the city are promising for SME's.

The results are supported by Alayuddin (2008) study that the length of a business's operation is its duration and can have an impact on a person's zakat compliance behavior. This is so that a business's stability can be gauged by how long it has been in operation.

Meanwhile, Kamarudin (2018) provides an explanation of the duration of business finding financial stability is the biggest obstacle in the first three years of business

operation, according to operations based on a start-up business graph created by Syamsul Anuar and cited by Kamarudin, 2018 enterprising people now attempt to put their concepts into practice and market their goods. Consequently, business owners must effectively manage their funds at this point in running their company.

Table 3.3 Business Profile in terms of Monthly Revenue

Monthly Revenue	f	%
₱250,000 and below	227	61
Above ₱ 2,000,000.00 to ₱ 8,000,000.00	20	5
Above ₱ 800,000.00 to ₱ 2,000,000.00	127	34
Overall Mean	374	100

The data from table 3.3 showed that most respondents earned less than ₱250,000.00 pesos monthly revenue with a frequency of 227 (61%). The second group earned between ₱800,000.00 and 2,000,000.00, with a frequency of 127 (34.0%). The final group earned between ₱2,000,000.00 and 8,000,000.00, with a frequency of 20 (5%).

The results imply that many businesses in San Pablo are considered as small scale enterprises because this is where business owners are visible and many are still starting from scratch, there are still more people with monthly incomes of 250,000 or less. In San Pablo City, Laguna, there are a lot of manufacturing companies that actually begin with a small investment and work their way up to a large income.

According to the Philippine Statistics Authority's (PSA) 2022 the country had 1,109,684 registered firms. Large firms account for 4,541 with MSMEs accounting for 1,105,143. The percentage of all establishments that are micro, 90.49% (1,004,195), small, 8.69% (96,464), and medium, 0.40% (4,484), are the next highest (DTI, 2021).

Table 4.1 Extent of Social Media Utilization in terms of Interactivity

Indicators	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
<i>I believe that utilizing social media...</i>			
1. allows my business to communicate directly with my target audience through comments, direct messages, or live chat features.	3.93	0.25	Very High Extent

2. helps me to gather valuable feedback from my customers essential in understanding their preferences, concerns, and making improvements on my products or services.	3.83	0.37	Very High Extent
3. facilitates the creation of communities, groups, forums and dedicated hash tags where my customers can engage with each other.	3.60	0.49	Very High Extent
4. helps me to actively involve the audience and boosts engagement	3.65	0.48	Very High Extent
5. allow me to showcase my brand personality and engaging content, humor, and a conversational tone help in humanizing the brand.	3.83	0.38	Very High Extent
Overall Mean	3.77	0.23	Very High Extent
<i>Legend: 3.51 – 4.00 Very High Extent; 2.51 – 3.50 High Extent; 1.51 – 2.50 Low Extent; 1.00 – 1.50 Very Low Extent</i>			

The data from table 4.1 presented an overall mean of 3.77 with an interpretation of “very high extent” on the extent of social media utilization in terms of interactivity. Allowing the business to directly communicate with the target audience is the highest indicator with a mean of 3.93 and a *sd* of 0.25. On the other hand, the lowest indicator is facilitating the creation of communities, groups, and forums to engage customers with a mean of 3.60 and a *sd* of 0.49.

The results imply that the lowest signal indicates how crucial it is for neighborhood groups to be aware of what is happening in one other's businesses, while the highest signal illustrates how advantageous it is for managers and business owners to communicate with customers more effectively over business conversations when they have problems.

The study is supported by Ismail (2018) who asserted that social media marketing facilitates consumer interaction, communication, and access to product imagery and information, hence increasing brand equity and ultimately improving product recognition. Social media marketing can be achieved through a wide range of channels, such as information sharing via blogs, forums, and online communities. In order to establish brand communities on the virtual level (sphere), a number of firms aim to increase the degrees of communication and interactions with customers.

Table 4.2 Extent of Social Media Utilization in terms of Informativeness

Indicators	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
<i>I believe that utilizing social media...</i>			
1. helps me educate the audience about industry trends, products, and relevant topics.	3.92	0.27	Very High Extent
2. helps me provide educational content that is of value to my audience, tutorials, and other informative resources related to my products or services.	3.79	0.41	Very High Extent
3. by sharing customer testimonials and success stories on social media serves as reliable proof and create positive impact to customers.	3.59	0.49	Very High Extent
4. using frequently asked questions (FAQs) and conduct Q&A ensure that customers have access to relevant information and clarifications.	3.63	0.48	Very High Extent
5. helps me to promote and host webinars or online events and allow me to dive deeper into specific topics and engage with my audience in a more comprehensive way.	3.68	0.47	Very High Extent
Overall Mean	3.72	0.24	Very High Extent

Legend: 3.51 – 4.00 Very High Extent; 2.51 – 3.50 High Extent; 1.51 – 2.50 Low Extent; 1.00 – 1.50 Very Low Extent

The data from table 4.2 presented an overall mean of 3.72 with an interpretation of “very high extent” on the extent of social media utilization in terms of informativeness. Educating the audience about industry trends, products, and relevant topics revealed as the highest indicator with a mean of 3.92 and a *sd* of 0.27. The lowest indicator having access to relevant information and clarifications with a mean of 3.63 and a *sd* of 0.48.

The results imply that in terms of informativeness the best way to help business owners and managers become knowledgeable about new products, trends, and business-related subjects is to teach them how to educate themselves so that they can tell others about how these things will benefit their companies. On the other hand, the most detrimental way to be informative is to share customer success stories and testimonials on social media because they provide trustworthy evidence and have a good effect on customers.

Table 4.3 Extent of Social Media Utilization in terms of Personalization

Indicators	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
<i>I believe that utilizing social media...</i>			
1. helps me provide tools to segment audiences based on demographics, interests, and behaviors that messages resonate with each group.	3.78	0.42	Very High Extent
2. allows me create and share customized content that aligns with the interests and preferences of my audience.	3.91	0.29	Very High Extent
3. encourages customers create and share content related to products or services not only serve as social proof but also personalize the brand experience.	3.55	0.50	Very High Extent
4. providing exclusive access new products or content creates a sense of exclusivity and makes customers feel valued and connected to the brand.	3.91	0.28	Very High Extent
5. helps me create a personalized email campaign to gather information from social media to inform the content.	3.81	0.39	Very High Extent
Overall Mean	3.79	0.20	Very High Extent
<i>Legend: 3.51 – 4.00 Very High Extent; 2.51 – 3.50 High Extent; 1.51 – 2.50 Low Extent; 1.00 – 1.50 Very Low Extent</i>			

The data from table 4.3 presented an overall mean of 3.79 with an interpretation of “very high extent” on the extent of social media utilization in terms of personalization. As indicated by the findings, the highest indicator is the development and distribution of tailored content that corresponds to the preferences and interests of the target audience with the mean of 3.91 and the *sd* of 0.29. Conversely, the lowest indicator is granting customers exclusive access to new products or content in order to foster a sense of exclusivity, value, and connection to the brand with the mean of 3.91 and the *sd* of 0.28.

The results imply that they come from producing material that appeals to clients' desires and helps them relate to current trends. The least favorable aspect is that it promotes users to produce and disseminate information about goods and services that not only acts as social proof but also adds personality to the brand experience. The degree and simplicity with which customers can access information and services from a brand's social media pages is known as personalization.

In the study supported by Seo et al. (2018), the purpose of the personalization component is to foster customer happiness through interaction and communication between the specific user and the business. Peer-to-peer communication between the

company and the individual user can help the customer feel valued and different from competitors by giving them a sense of being heard.

Table 4.4 Extent of Social Media Utilization in terms of Trendiness

Indicators	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
<i>I believe that utilizing social media...</i>			
1. helps my business to track the performance of my content and identify what is working well and stay on top of trends.	3.69	0.46	Very High Extent
2. helps participate and boost my business by visibility and engagement creating content incorporating trending elements into my marketing strategies.	3.71	0.45	Very High Extent
3. to introduce new features and content formats regularly can leverage my business trends and interact with my audience.	3.83	0.38	Very High Extent
4. provide my business the ability to share real-time updates and allow quick adaptation to trends, industry news, and current events.	3.68	0.47	Very High Extent
5. by partnering with influencers who have a strong presence on social media will give my business access to a larger audience.	3.85	0.35	Very High Extent
Overall Mean	3.75	0.23	Very High Extent

Legend: 3.51 – 4.00 Very High Extent; 2.51 – 3.50 High Extent; 1.51 – 2.50 Low Extent; 1.00 – 1.50 Very Low Extent

The data from table 4.4 presented an overall mean of 3.75 with an interpretation of “very high extent” the extent of social media utilization in terms of trendiness. Collaborating with influential individuals to enable access to a larger audience is the most significant factor with a mean of 3.85 and a *sd* of 0.35. On the other hand, the ability to share real-time updates and quickly adapt to trends is the least important factor for social media utilization, with a mean of 3.68 and a *sd* of 0.47.

The results imply that social media platforms employ algorithms to determine hot subjects and keywords, which leads to trending content. These algorithms are made to examine the activity, including the quantity of shares, likes, comments, and searches. This identifies the subjects and content that are causing the most amount of interaction. A topic is designated as trending and prominently featured on the platform's homepage after it achieves a specific level of engagement.

Table 4.5 Extent of Social Media Utilization in terms of Word of Mouth

Indicators	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
<i>I believe that utilizing social media in marketing...</i>			
1. leverages word of mouth marketing to promote our products and services.	3.90	0.30	Very High Extent
2. through social media influencers enhance the impact of word-of-mouth referrals.	3.67	0.47	Very High Extent
3. actively encourages our consumers to post positive experiences on social media platforms.	3.72	0.45	Very High Extent
4. assists in the proactive monitoring and response to consumer comments, reviews, and recommendations on social media platforms.	3.96	0.20	Very High Extent
5. leads to customer testimonials and shared experiences and become a means to augment our word-of-mouth marketing endeavors.	3.74	0.44	Very High Extent
Overall Mean	3.80	0.16	Very High Extent

Legend: 3.51 – 4.00 Very High Extent; 2.51 – 3.50 High Extent; 1.51 – 2.50 Low Extent; 1.00 – 1.50 Very Low Extent

The data from table 4.5 presented an overall mean of 3.80 with an interpretation of “very high extent” on the extent of social media utilization in terms of word of mouth. The highest indicator, with a mean of 3.96 and an *sd* of 0.20, is proactive monitoring and reaction to consumer comments, reviews, and recommendations on social media platforms. On the other hand, the least significant measure is the increase in the effectiveness of word-of-mouth recommendations through social media influencers, with an average score of 3.67 and an *sd* of 0.47.

The results imply that the best way to measure word-of-mouth marketing is to use it to support proactive social media platform monitoring and customer comments, reviews, and recommendations. Conversely, the weakest finding suggests that social media influencers amplify the effects of word-of-mouth recommendations.

The term "e-WOM" refers to any consumer-generated content, whether favorable or unfavorable, that is shared online with other consumers (Chu & Sung, 2018). Consumers talking to consumers about brands are known as e-WOM in social media usage

Table 5.1 Test of Difference between the Utilization of Social Media Marketing in SMEs when Grouped According to Nature of Business

Variable	H-Value	P-Value	Decision	Interpretation
Interactivity	176.34	0.00	Reject Ho	Significant
Informativeness	173.97	0.00	Reject Ho	Significant
Word of mouth	127.19	0.00	Reject Ho	Significant
Personalization	159.73	0.00	Reject Ho	Significant
Trendiness	142.82	0.00	Reject Ho	Significant

Legend: $p < 0.05$ Significant; $p \geq 0.05$ Not Significant

The data from table 5.1 presented the results of a statistical test comparing the use of social media marketing in the selected enterprises based on their business nature. Given that the p-value for all variables is 0, the appropriate course of action is to reject the null hypothesis. All of these variables show highly significant differences between the groups.

Based on the data, it can be concluded that P values are zero (0) for all evaluated variables, such as interactivity, trendiness, personalization, informativeness, and word of mouth. This implies that there is no visible variation in the use of social media marketing based on the type of business.

The study supported by the List of Establishments report from the Department of Trade and Industry (2020) states that there are 957,620 registered commercial enterprises in the nation. Of them, 99.51% are MSMEs and 0.49% are major firms. 88.77% of MSMEs are microenterprises, 10.25% are small businesses, and 0.49% are medium-sized businesses. The top industry sectors, which accounted for approximately 83.77% of all MSME establishments, are (1) wholesale and retail trade; (2) accommodation and food service activities (134,046); (3) manufacturing (110,916); (4) other service activities (62,376); and (5) financial and insurance activities (45,558). Repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles (445,386) is another prominent industry sector. Before the pandemic, MSMEs created about 5.38 million jobs, or 62.66% of all occupations in the nation. Microenterprises accounted for 29.38% of these jobs, followed by 25.78% and 7.50%.

Table 5.2 Test of Difference between the Utilization of Social Media Marketing in SMEs when Grouped According to Years of Operation

Variable	H-Value	P-Value	Decision	Interpretation
Interactivity	78.89	0.00	Reject Ho	Significant
Informativeness	113.05	0.00	Reject Ho	Significant
Word of mouth	53.91	0.00	Reject Ho	Significant
Personalization	90.51	0.00	Reject Ho	Significant
Trendiness	57.56	0.00	Reject Ho	Significant

Legend: $p < 0.05$ Significant; $p \geq 0.05$ Not Significant

The data from table 5.2 displayed the results of a test comparing the use of social media marketing in the selected enterprises based on the number of years they have been in operation. Since the p-value for all variables is 0, it is appropriate to reject the null hypothesis. Similarly, with the previous table, all of these variables show significant differences between the groups.

All of the variables that were tested in terms of the social media marketing activities show that. The choice is to reject the hypothesis because the P-values are zero. This suggests that the use of social media marketing does significantly differ based on the number of years of business.

The study supported by Shinozaki and Rao (2020) reported that 59.6% of the MSMEs surveyed had been in business for less than 5 yrs. (start-ups primarily micro-enterprises and in services). These were followed by those that had been in business for six to ten years (18.8%), eleven to fifteen years (8.5%), sixteen to thirty years (9.6%), and more than thirty years (3.4%). A female head was present in over half (56.1%) of the MSMEs surveyed. Women owned MSMEs made up 59% of micro-enterprises, 51% of small business, and 17% of medium enterprises, according to company size. They made up 56.0% of businesses in the manufacturing sector, which was followed by businesses in the service sector (58.1%). In the agricultural sector, women owned 44.4% of the businesses, a smaller ratio than in other industries.

Table 5.3 Test of Difference between the Utilization of Social Media Marketing in SMEs when Grouped According to Monthly Revenue

Variable	H-Value	P-Value	Decision	Interpretation
Interactivity	127.97	0.00	Reject Ho	Significant
Informativeness	128.41	0.00	Reject Ho	Significant
Word of mouth	113.99	0.00	Reject Ho	Significant
Personalization	171.26	0.00	Reject Ho	Significant
Trendiness	91.32	0.00	Reject Ho	Significant

Legend: $p < 0.05$ Significant; $p \geq 0.05$ Not Significant

The data from table 5.3 presented the results of a statistical test comparing the use of social media marketing in the selected enterprises based on their monthly revenue. Considering that the p-values for all variables are zero, rejecting the null hypothesis is the appropriate statistical decision. All of these variables show highly significant differences.

The information suggests that the hypothesis should be rejected because the P-values for every variable examined interactivity, informativeness, personalization, trendiness, and word-of-mouth were below the P-value of 0.5. This implies that there is sufficient evidence to say that monthly income affects the utilization of SMM in SME's.

The study supported by Shinozaki and Rao's (2021) findings, over ½ (61%) of the companies reported average revenue wages of no more than 9,000 pesos. Then came

35.1%, whose average monthly salary fell between 9,001 and 18,000. Less than 5% of the sample consisted of companies paying an average monthly salary of more than 18,001. Notably, the average wage at more than 4/5 of the businesses in Region 1 (83.7%) and Region 9 (Zamboanga Peninsula, 82.8%) was less than 9,000. In contrast, the only regions with businesses reporting monthly pay of more than 27,000 were the NCR, Region 4-A, Region 5 (Bicol), and Region 10.

According to Abrigo (2020) asserts that as an organization grows in size, the average monthly wage tends to climb. From 3% for micro-enterprises to 11.0% for small and 20% for medium-sized enterprises, the percentage of businesses with average salaries above P18,000 grew. On the other hand, the proportion of businesses with an average salary of no more than P9,000 dropped from 67.6% for micro, to 29.9% for small, and to just 24.0% for medium-sized businesses. By sector, a comparable pattern was seen. From 72% in agriculture to 66% in manufacturing and 55% in services, the percentage of businesses with an average salary of less than P9, 000 decreased. On the other hand, almost 50% of the businesses in all three sectors stated that their average salary was no higher than P9, 000.

Conclusions

The study determined the utilization of social media marketing in the selected enterprises in the City of San Pablo, Laguna. This study presented the business profile of the respondents namely, nature of business, years of operation and monthly revenue toward social media marketing activities in terms of interactivity, informativeness, personalization, trendiness and word of mouth. A researcher made a questionnaire administered to the 374 respondents, both owners and managers of SME's.

Based on the results the majority of respondents in the nature of business category belonged to the manufacturing sector, followed by those with 10 years or less of operation, and finally, those with monthly revenue under 250,000.00 and below. This information was derived from the owners' and managers' business profiles.

All of the variables that measured the extent that social media marketing was used interactivity, informativeness, personalization, trendiness, and word-of-mouth had higher composite means and were interpreted as highly significant.

The generated computed probability values on the utilization of social media marketing when grouped according to their business profile of respondents where nature of business, years in operation and monthly revenue is .000,.000,.000,.000,.000 respectively. The null hypothesis was rejected because the five variables' estimated probability values were less than the 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, there were significant differences in the perceptions of the respondents when grouped according to business profile nature of business in terms of interactivity, informativeness, personalization, trendiness, and word of mouth.

Based on the aforementioned findings of the study, the data analysis leads to the conclusion that the results validate the hypothesis that was developed for this investigation. The stated hypothesis is there is a significant difference between the utilization of social media marketing when grouped according to the business profile of the respondents. It has been confirmed that social media marketing in the selected enterprises in the City of San Pablo, Laguna, was perceived to have benefits including interactivity, informativeness, personalization, trendiness, and word of mouth to a very high extent. Nonetheless, the majority of users say they are happy with the tools that social media marketing offers and want to maintain the techniques that are attainable but not measurable for their businesses to a very high extent.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions drawn from the study on the utilization of social media marketing in the selected enterprises in the city of San Pablo, Laguna the following recommendations are provided:

SMEs Owners and Managers. Make use of the various accessible business strategies. Utilize social media marketing strategies for your company to help it expand into new markets for goods, services, and innovation. It generates prospects for accumulating wealth and increasing income. It fosters freedom and initiative while also creating opportunity.

Local Government Unit of San Pablo City, Laguna. The researcher recommends that local collaborations for economic growth be supported by the government. The municipal administration should plan how to work with the chosen businesses to form alliances for regional economic growth. These alliances may make it easier for the businesses to buy items and services together, which would raise demand for those goods and services.

Future researchers. Make use of this study as a platform for other research endeavors. It has the potential to be a further source of information that researchers who wish to organize a study on a related topic can use as a reference for their next research.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers obtained informed consent of the respondents and notified them of their freedom to withdraw from the study at any time. Their anonymity was maintained and their well-being was protected. There was no conflict of interest in the conduct of the study. Plagiarism was strictly avoided and there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings. Finally, the results were used purely for research.

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